

A high-quality draft genome for *Melaleuca alternifolia* (tea tree) - a new platform for evolutionary genomics of myrtaceous terpene-rich species

Julia Voelker^{1,2}, Mervyn Shepherd^{1,3} and Ramil Mauleon^{1,4}

¹Faculty of Science and Engineering, Southern Cross University,
Military Road, East Lismore NSW 2480, Australia

²Julia Voelker (corresponding author)

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7615-0553>

e-mail: j.voelker.10@student.scu.edu.au

³ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8708-4670>

⁴ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8512-144X>

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1 Abstract

2 *Melaleuca alternifolia* (tea tree) is an Australian native tree, which is the source of a renowned
3 terpene-rich essential oil used in therapeutic and cosmetic products around the world. Tea tree has
4 been cultivated and bred in Australia since the 1990's, and because of its economic importance, along
5 with its *Eucalyptus* and *Corymbia* spp relatives, is one of the most extensively studied members of the
6 Myrtaceae family for genetics and biochemistry of terpene biosynthesis. Here, a high-quality *de novo*
7 genome assembly using PacBio and Illumina sequencing data is reported as a platform for comparative
8 genomics in the Myrtaceae. The genome was assembled into 3,128 scaffolds with a total length of
9 362 Mb (N50 = 1.9 Mb) and had significantly higher contiguity than a previously reported assembly
10 (N50 = 8.7 Kb) based on short Illumina paired-end reads. A total of 37,226 protein-coding genes were
11 predicted, using a homology-based, RNAseq evidence-based and *ab initio* prediction approach.
12 Genome assembly and annotation exhibited high completeness scores of 98.1% and 89.4%,
13 respectively, when compared to the eudicot BUSCO database. The contiguity of the sequence was
14 sufficient to reveal extensive gene order conservation and detection of chromosomal rearrangements
15 in alignments with *E. grandis* and *C. citriodora* genomes. This new genome provides an enhanced
16 resource to investigate the genome structure and gene family evolution of *M. alternifolia*, which will
17 enable further comparative genomic studies in the family of Myrtaceae, and help to elucidate the
18 genetic foundations of economically valuable traits in this essential oil crop.

19

20 Introduction

21 *Melaleuca alternifolia* (Maiden and Betche) Cheel, (tea tree), is a shrub or small tree that is native to
22 southern Queensland and northern New South Wales regions of Australia [1]. It belongs to the
23 Myrtaceae, a large angiosperm family of Southern hemisphere origin, encompassing 142 genera and
24 over 5,500 species [2]. The Myrtaceae are notable in that many species produce high concentrations

25 of volatile terpenoid compounds usually stored in schizogenous secretory cavities in their leaves [1].
26 Of the 17 tribes, the Melelaeucae, Eucalypteae and Myrteae have the highest diversity of unique
27 mono- and sesquiterpenoid compounds in their leaf oils [3]. These oils are thought to have important
28 adaptive roles, functioning in plant defence against pests and protection against abiotic stresses [4,
29 5]. The oil is also distilled from the leaves of a number of species and used in medicinal, therapeutic
30 and cosmetic products [2]. The cultivation of *M. alternifolia* and production of tea tree oil is one of the
31 more important industries based on an essential oil from a myrtaceous species in Australia and
32 overseas [1].

33 Here we report a *de novo* high quality draft assembly of the *M. alternifolia* genome, using the short
34 sequencing reads from an earlier draft genome [6] in conjunction with newly generated PacBio single-
35 molecule real-time (SMRT) sequencing reads. This new draft assembly resulted in a genome size of
36 362 Mb, which was close to the size of the previous assembly (356.5 Mb) [6] and the physical size
37 estimated from flow cytometry (357 Mb) [7]. The overall assembly statistics were improved by using
38 the longer sequencing reads, with an N50 of the assembled scaffolds at 1.9 Mb, which is about 214
39 times higher than the N50 achieved by Calvert *et al.* [6]. The BUSCO score for the genome, which
40 assesses the presence of single-copy orthologs [8], was also increased from 86.3% to 98.1%. The
41 subsequent gene annotation led to the prediction of more than 37,000 genes, and a high level of
42 ortholog completeness (89.4%) was confirmed for the predicted proteome. Furthermore, the
43 organisation of genes could be resolved in more detail, with many long scaffolds showing synteny to
44 *E. grandis* chromosomes.

45 This new genome sequence for tea tree should meet our aim to generate a resource for comparative
46 studies with other Myrtaceae to investigate mechanisms of genome evolution in this group. We are
47 especially interested in mechanisms underlying gene family evolution and in particular the terpene
48 synthase (TPS) gene family. This gene family is responsible for the final stages of terpene biosynthesis
49 and is highly diversified in plants [9]. Tandem duplication is thought to be an important mechanism

50 for gene family evolution in the *TPS* family, and more broadly for adaptive genes in long-lived eucalypts
51 and other tree groups [10]. An earlier analysis of the *TPS* gene family in *M. alternifolia* revealed
52 relatively few *TPS* compared with other myrtaceous species [6]. This new, more contiguous genome
53 will allow us to more confidently explore questions on gene family size and microsynteny analysis in
54 tea tree.

55 Methods

56 DNA extraction

57 Fresh young foliage was collected from the reference genotype SCU1 of *Melaleuca alternifolia*, the
58 same individual used by Calvert *et al.* [6] for Illumina sequencing. In order to yield high-quality DNA
59 for PacBio sequencing, the CTAB extraction protocol from Healey *et al.* [11] was used with
60 modifications as mentioned in the supplementary material [12].

61 The quantity of extracted DNA was measured fluorometrically with a Qubit BR assay (Invitrogen), and
62 the quality was assessed using a Nanodrop (Thermo Scientific). Furthermore, the integrity of the DNA
63 was examined on a 0.5% Agarose gel.

64 DNA sequencing

65 The DNA sample was sent to the Ramaciotti Centre for Genomics (University of NSW, Sydney), which
66 undertook further quality control with Pippin Pulse gel electrophoresis (Sage Science).

67 DNA was concentrated to 200-250 ng/ μ l using AMPure PB beads (Pacific Biosciences) at the
68 Ramaciotti Centre for Genomics so that it was suitable for library preparation, where the aim was for

69 DNA fragments of 20-50 Kb. The gDNA fragments were sequenced using 2 PacBio Sequel SMRT cells
70 and the raw sequencing reads are available from the NCBI BioProject PRJNA702189.

71 **Genome assembly**

72 Prior to assembly, all reads were mapped to the reference sequence of the *E. grandis* chloroplast
73 (GenBank accession MG925369.1) using minimap2 v2.17-r941 (RRID:SCR_018550) [13]. Reads aligning
74 with more than 80% of their length were filtered out and the remaining reads were used for the
75 nuclear genome assembly.

76 With the current advancements in sequencing technologies, many tools have been developed to meet
77 the demand for long-read assemblers, using different assembly algorithms [14, 15]. However, not all
78 of them are suited for a diploid, heterozygous plant genome. Hence, three different assembly methods
79 were carried out in order to compare their performance and select the most suitable tool. Those three
80 tools were 1) Canu v1.8 (RRID:SCR_015880), long-read assembler [16]; 2) Flye v2.5
81 (RRID:SCR_017016), long-read assembler [17]; 3) MaSuRCA v3.4.0 (RRID:SCR_010691), hybrid
82 assembler using long-reads and Illumina short-reads [18]. For the MaSuRCA genome assembly, the
83 available short paired-end reads from the same genotype [6], were incorporated into the assembly.
84 Prior to assembly, BBTools v38.50 (RRID:SCR_016968) [19] was used to filter Illumina reads for
85 sequences of at least 75 bp length, and duplicate reads were removed using FastUniq
86 (RRID:SCR_000682) [20]. Four libraries were available, with insert sizes of 350 bp, 550 bp, 300 bp, and
87 700 bp, respectively.

88 For each assembly, the completeness was assessed using Quast v5.0.2 (RRID:SCR_001228) [21] and
89 BUSCO (Galaxy Version 4.1.2, eudicot-odb10 database, RRID:SCR_015008) [8]. The most suitable
90 assembly tool was selected based on overall assembly length, best BUSCO score and indicators of
91 contiguity, such as N50, NG50, L50, and LG50 values.

92 Furthermore, the selected assembly was screened for contaminations with BlobTools v1.1.1
93 (RRID:SCR_017618) [22]. The NCBI nucleotide (nt) database (downloaded 07/2020) was used as

94 reference for BLASTn v2.9.0+ (RRID:SCR_001598) [23], while the UniProt reference proteomes
95 (release 05/2020) were input for Diamond blastx v0.9.24 [24]. The required coverage files were
96 created with minimap2 and SAMtools v1.9 (RRID:SCR_002105) [25]. The final genome assembly post
97 contaminant removal was deposited at NCBI GenBank as accession version JAGKPW010000000.

98 The heterozygosity of the genome was calculated by aligning the Illumina paired-end libraries to the
99 final assembly using minimap2. The alignment files were assigned to read groups with Picard v2.23.8
100 (RRID:SCR_006525) [26], and variants were called using The Genome Analysis Toolkit (GATK v4.1.9.0,
101 RRID:SCR_001876). The heterozygosity ratio was calculated as the number of heterozygous sites in
102 comparison to the total number of nucleotides in the assembly.

103 Gene prediction

104 The Fgenesh++ v7.2.2 pipeline (RRID:SCR_018928) [27] was used to predict genes in the assembled
105 scaffolds. The NCBI non-redundant plant protein database (provided by Softberry), the *Eucalyptus*
106 *grandis* gene matrix (purchased by the Australian BioCommons), and RNAseq spliced read alignments
107 were provided as evidence. For the RNA evidence, the *M. alternifolia* RNAseq data from three other
108 individual trees of the same chemotype (BioProject PRJNA388506; SRR5630605, SRR5630611,
109 SRR5630622) were downloaded and converted to fastq format with the NCBI SRA toolkit. They were
110 subjected to quality controls using FastQC (RRID:SCR_014583) and trimming with Flexbar
111 (RRID:SCR_013001) [28], following the method by Padovan *et al.* [29]. They were then aligned to the
112 genome using ReadsMap (v1.10.1). Upon completion of the Fgenesh++ run, the predicted genes were
113 filtered to remove incomplete gene models (missing start- and/or stop-codon) and genes coinciding
114 with repeat regions. Transposable elements in the assembled genome were first identified with
115 RepeatModeler v2.0.1 (RRID:SCR_015027), RepeatMasker v4.1.0 (RRID:SCR_012954) and the Dfam
116 3.1 database. Genes containing a full-length transposon or having at least 20% of their sequence
117 overlapping with repeat regions were determined with Bedtools intersect v2.29.2 (RRID:SCR_006646).
118 With the exception of sequences containing Pfam domains that are not related to transposable

119 elements, the identified genes were removed from the prediction. Gene prediction statistics were
120 assessed with BUSCO (proteome mode), InterProScan (Galaxy version 5.0.0, RRID:SCR_005829) [30]
121 and AGAT v.0.5.1 [31]. With InterProScan, a similarity-based approach was used to screen predicted
122 proteins for sequences listed in the PfamA database (RRID:SCR_004726) [32]. Furthermore, using the
123 taxonomy search of the Pfam database [33], a list of protein families known to be present in
124 eudicotyledons was created to assess which InterProScan results contained those eudicot protein
125 families.

126 Synteny with eucalypts and whole genome alignments

127 The predicted coding sequences (CDS) were aligned to eucalypt reference CDS using CoGe SynMap
128 [34]. Default parameters were retained, allowing a maximum distance of 20 genes between two
129 matches and five genes as the minimum number of aligned pairs. Reference sequences were the
130 unmasked CDS (v2.0, id35018) of *E. grandis* strain BRASUZ1 (id35288), and the unmasked CDS (v1.1,
131 id28779) of *Corymbia citriodora* subsp. *variegata* (id40461, unpublished). The CDS of *Populus*
132 *trichocarpa* v3 (id38424) was used for comparison.

133 In addition to the screen for syntenic gene regions, pair-wise whole genome alignments of *M.*
134 *alternifolia* were also carried out with *E. grandis* and *C. citriodora* pseudo-chromosomes. The genomes
135 were aligned in NUCmer (Nucleotide mummer v3.1, RRID:SCR_018171), with the --mum --minmatch
136 40 --mincluster 100 options, and matches were visualised using Mummerplot (v3.5).

137 Orthogroup discovery

138 OrthoFinder v2.5.2 (RRID:SCR_017118) [35, 36] was used to discover orthogroups among the protein
139 sequences of selected species and infer phylogenetic relationships. The proteomes of *Arabidopsis*
140 *thaliana* ARAPORT11 [37], *E. grandis* v2.0 [38], *Populus trichocarpa* v4.1 [39], *Salix purpurea* v1 [40]
141 and *Vitis vinifera* v2.1 [41] were obtained from Phytozome, using the primary transcripts only.
142 OrthoFinder was run with default settings to compare the mentioned species with the *C. citriodora*

143 primary transcripts [42] and *M. alternifolia* protein sequences. Resulting phylogenetic trees were
144 visualised with Dendroscope v3.7.3 [43].

145 Results & Discussion

146 *A de novo genome assembly for Melaleuca alternifolia*

147 The modified DNA extraction protocol yielded high-molecular-weight (HMW) DNA of high purity
148 (260:280 ratio = 1.86, 260:230 ratio = 2.01). As confirmed by the Pippin Pulse gel electrophoresis, the
149 gDNA was highly intact with a size greater than 40 Kb. The subsequent PacBio sequencing resulted in
150 a total of 1,831,348 reads, with a GC-content of 42%, individual sequence lengths between 50-
151 71,437 bp and a total length of 19,732,598,005 bp. Based on a flow cytometry genome size estimate
152 of 356.97 Mb, this implies a genome coverage (sequencing depth) of around 55x.

153 After sequencing, the tea tree genome was assembled with the three different tools Canu, Flye and
154 MaSuRCA. For the MaSuRCA assembly, the Illumina sequencing reads [6] were included, which
155 covered the genome more than 300x. Overall, the MaSuRCA assembly had the most favourable
156 assembly and completeness statistics, in addition to having the assembly size (365 Mb) that was
157 closest to the flow cytometry estimate (357 Mb) and the Illumina assembly length of 356.5 Mb [6, 7]
158 (Table 1). The N50 for the MaSuRCA assembly was 214 times higher than that for the earlier genome
159 assembly by Calvert *et al.* [6] (N50=9 Kb), representing a significant improvement in scaffold length
160 due to the long-read sequencing approach. The N50 of the MaSuRCA assembly (N50=1,883 Kb), also
161 exceeded the N50 values for the Canu and Flye assemblies, which were 865 Kb and 571 Kb,
162 respectively (Table 1).

163 Each of the three assemblies was also assessed in a BUSCO analysis for their completeness of
164 orthologous sequences. The MaSuRCA assembly had the highest score (98.1%) for complete BUSCO
165 groups, followed by Canu (97.3%) and Flye (96.9%) (Table 1). The MaSuRCA assembly also contained
166 the fewest fragmented and missing reference genes (1.9 %), but the lowest proportion of duplicated

167 orthologs was found in the Flye assembly (3.1%) (Table 1). In contrast to the other assemblies, the
 168 Canu assembly was notable in having a much higher percentage (24%) of complete but duplicated
 169 BUSCOs. Taken together with the notably larger total assembly length for the Canu assembly (451 Mb)
 170 relative to the other approaches, this high percentage of duplicated sequences was thought to suggest
 171 that Canu might have assembled more than one haplotype [44].

172 Given the higher contiguity and completeness of the MaSuRCA assembly relative to the other
 173 assemblies, it was used for further analyses.

174

175 **Table 1 Comparison of the different *M. alternifolia de novo* assemblies**

Assembly	Length [Mb]	No. of scaffolds	N50 ^a [Kb]	NG50 ^b [Kb]	BUSCO score ^c (eudicot_odb10)
Canu	451.93	3,429	864.59	1,331.08	C:97.3%(S:72.7%,D:24.6%),F:0.8%,M:1.9%
Flye	328.17	2,197	570.96	489.41	C:96.9%(S:93.8%,D:3.1%), F:0.9%,M:2.2%
MaSuRCA	365.23	3,217	1,882.57	1,911.23	C:98.1%(S:91.2%,D:6.9%), F:0.6%,M:1.3%
Illumina draft ^d	356.50	221,396	8.78	8.75	C:86.3%(S:84.5%,D:1.8%), F:6.2%,M:7.5%

176 ^aN50: the collection of all contigs of that length or longer covers at least half of the genome assembly; ^bNG50:
 177 the collection of all contigs of that length or longer covers at least half of the expected genome size of 357 Mb;
 178 ^cC: complete, S: single-copy, D: duplicated, F: fragmented, M: missing; ^d by Calvert *et al.* [6]

179

180 A screen for contaminating sequences from other species using BlobTools identified 60 contaminated
 181 scaffolds in the MaSuRCA assembly (Figure 1). These sequences were classified as bacterial, viral or
 182 fungal. However, they only represented 0.3% of the total assembly length, and the majority of the
 183 assembly (353.6 Mb) was identified as plant sequences. Based on this screening, contaminated
 184 scaffolds were removed, while all scaffolds listed as Streptophyta or with no hits to the databases
 185 were retained. Of the raw sequencing reads used in the assembly, 97.68% mapped to the scaffolds,

186 and only 0.03 were found to map to contaminated sequences. A further contaminant screen upon
 187 submission of the assembly to the NCBI GenBank portal led to the exclusion of 29 scaffolds that
 188 seemed to be of mitochondrial or chloroplast origin.

189

190

191 **Figure 1** BlobPlot showing potential contaminations in the assembled MaSuRCA scaffolds. Each dot represents
 192 a single scaffold, and the larger the dot, the longer the represented scaffold sequence. Scaffolds were assigned
 193 to taxonomic groups based on their alignment to the NCBI nucleotide database and the UniProt protein
 194 database. The scaffold coverage is based on alignments of the raw sequencing reads to the assembled scaffolds.

195

196 After removing identified contaminations, new assembly statistics were created in Quast (Table 2). A
 197 BUSCO analysis on the filtered genome assembly showed a high level of completeness with 2,282
 198 (98.1%) of the 2,326 BUSCO groups being reported as complete (Table 2). The majority (91.1%) were
 199 single-copy orthologs. Variant calling in Illumina reads aligned to the assembled sequence revealed a
 200 heterozygosity rate of 0.6% for this *M. alternifolia* individual.

201

202 **Table 2 Final assembly statistics for the filtered MaSuRCA scaffolds, created with Quast and BUSCO analyses.**

Characteristic	MaSuRCA scaffolds
No. of scaffolds	3,128
Largest scaffold	11,132,794 bp
Total length	362,036,213bp
GC	40.35%
N50	1,894,811 bp
N75	594,516 bp
L50	54
L75	135
No. of N's per 100 Kb	3.90
Complete and single-copy BUSCOs	2,120 (91.1%)
Complete and duplicated BUSCOs	162 (7%)
Fragmented BUSCOs	14 (0.6%)
Missing BUSCOs	30 (1.3%)
Total BUSCO groups searched	2,326 (eudictos_odb10)

203

204

205 [Fgenesh++ prediction results](#)

206 A total number of 52,135 protein-coding genes were predicted by Fgenesh++, of which 23,920 were
 207 predicted based on protein evidence (high sequence similarity to NCBI nr-protein plant DB), with the
 208 remaining genes being predicted *de novo*. A total of 2,170 genes had missing start- or stop-codons

209 (Table 3). A further 12,739 genes were excluded due to overlaps with transposable elements, resulting
210 in a filtered set of 37,226 complete gene models.

211 A BUSCO assessment of the translated sequences revealed an overall high level of ortholog
212 completeness in the proteome after filtering the predictions (89.4%), with most of them being single-
213 copy (Table 3). Furthermore, a screen against the reference database of PfamA protein families
214 showed that 64.39% of all proteins contain known eudicot Pfam domains.

215

216 **Table 3 FgenesH++ gene prediction results**

Trait	Count
No. of predicted protein-coding genes	52,135
Genes without start- and stop-codon	29
Genes without start-codon	460
Genes without stop-codon	1,681
Overlapping with transposable elements	12,739
Genes remaining after filtering	37,226
No. of proteins with hit to Pfam domains	26,415
No. of proteins with hit to eudicot Pfam domains	23,970
Percentage of genes with eudicot Pfam domains	64.39%
Mean gene length	2,791 bp
Complete and single-copy BUSCOs	1,938 (83.3%)
Complete and duplicated BUSCOs	141 (6.1%)
Fragmented BUSCOs	114 (4.9%)
Missing BUSCOs	133 (5.7%)
Total BUSCO groups searched (eudicots_odb10)	2,326

217

218

219 Synteny to eucalypts

220 The predicted coding sequences (CDS) of *M. alternifolia* were aligned to eucalyptus reference CDS
221 using CoGe Synmap. The resulting syntenic map showed a high level of collinearity in the gene order
222 of *M. alternifolia* and *E. grandis* (Figure 2). The assembled scaffolds of sufficient size reveal
223 rearrangements on the chromosome scale; some inversions in the tea tree genome were evident (*E.*
224 *grandis* chromosome one), together with one translocation between the *E. grandis* chromosomes
225 eight and six. The comparison to the *C. citriodora* CDS showed a similar plot but the number of gaps
226 seems to be increased, especially on the *C. citriodora* chromosomes 4 and 5 (Supplementary figure 1).
227 Furthermore, a comparison between *M. alternifolia* and *P. trichocarpa* revealed that synteny is still
228 identifiable between these two rosids. Nevertheless, the synteny was reduced with larger genetic
229 distance, leading to translocations and inversions being more notable than among the examined
230 Myrtaceae (Supplementary figure 2).

231 **Figure 2** Syntenic Map (SynMap) of the predicted coding sequences of *M. alternifolia* and *E. grandis*. The syntenic
232 path assembly shows the *M. alternifolia* scaffolds (y-axis) ordered according to their synteny to the *E. grandis*
233 chromosomes (x-axis), which were ordered numerically. Each green dot represents a syntenic gene region. The
234 *E. grandis* scaffolds that are not part of the chromosome-scale assembly are displayed at the end of the x-axis
235 (grey area).

237 The whole-genome alignments with Mummerplot resulted in similar findings, with an overall high
238 sequence similarity among the compared Myrtaceae, with more inversions in the tea tree alignment
239 to *C. citriodora* than to *E. grandis* (Supplementary figures 3 and 4). The underlying cause of the
240 different densities in the pairwise synplots between *Melaleuca*, *Corymbia* and *Eucalyptus*, and
241 differences in the rearrangements detected between the pairs will require more investigation.

242 *M. alternifolia* is an ideal model species to compare genomic features with eucalypts. The two tribes
243 Melaleuceae and Eucalypteae share some anatomical features, such as capsular fruit, the abundance
244 of oil-glands in their leaves, and epicormic buds underneath their bark [1, 2], and their sequence
245 similarities are expected to be high, with genetic markers being transferable to some extent [45]. The
246 syntenic comparisons and whole-genome alignments of our study confirmed these expectations.

247 Orthogroup discovery

248 The inference of phylogenetic relationships and the discovery of orthogroups based on the sequences
249 of selected species affirmed the fgenes++ gene prediction results for *M. alternifolia*.

250 OrthoFinder assigned 248,528 genes (91.3% of total) to 29,672 orthogroups. Of these, 10,982
251 orthogroups contained genes from all eight species, while 4,386 groups were species-specific. Most
252 of the *M. alternifolia* genes (78%) were assigned to orthogroups with two or more species present
253 (see Supplementary table 1 and 2 for more OrthoFinder-related statistics).

254 Based on the gene trees created by OrthoFinder for the eight selected species, phylogenetic
255 relationship were inferred [35]. The resulting species tree showed *Arabidopsis* as outgroup, while the
256 Myrtaceae members *E. grandis*, *C. citriodora* and *M. alternifolia* form a clade that separated from the
257 other rosids *P. trichocarpa*, *S. purpurea* and *V. vinifera* (Figure 3).

258

259 **Figure 3** Species tree as inferred by OrthoFinder with branch lengths based on substitutions per site.

260

261 Further investigations of the *M. alternifolia* sequences should be conducted to understand the
 262 dynamics of gene family evolution in this species, especially in comparison to other Myrtaceae.

263 The genome of tea tree will make a valuable addition to the growing quiver of sequences available for
 264 Myrtaceae. So far, genomic studies on Myrtaceae have mainly been motivated by the economic
 265 importance of some species and the relevance to identify the genetic foundations of specific traits
 266 [46]. Hence, the genomes of *E. grandis* and *E. globulus* were the first trees of the family Myrtaceae
 267 sequenced [38] but were soon followed by the genome of a sister genus, *C. citriodora* [42, 47]. Due to
 268 their geographical isolation and thus separated evolution in Australia, eucalypts are a model taxon for
 269 comparative genomic studies to find shared evolutionary history, but also unique genome
 270 characteristics, in comparison to other woody perennials of the rosoid lineage, such as *Populus* and
 271 *Vitis vinifera* [38].

272 In addition to providing an outgroup for phylogenetic analyses of derived and ancestral characters in
 273 the eucalypts, the *M. alternifolia* genome will be a resource for helping to elucidate genomic
 274 responses to adaptive pressures among the Myrtaceae evolving on the Australian continent.

275 Although much remains uncertain regarding the evolutionary history of the *Melaleuca*, the genera
276 *Eucalyptus* and *Melaleuca* are thought to have had a shared ancestry until 68 Ma [48], and current
277 evidence suggests that *Melaleuca* and *Eucalyptus* largely adapted to contrasting environments [49].
278 The majority of the genus *Melaleuca* are small trees or shrubs that grow in wetland or periodically
279 waterlogged habitats [1], and have developed adaptations consistent with their waterlogged life
280 history; i.e. *Melaleuca* trees are capable of gas exchange through their bark [50], and seedlings
281 developed aquatic roots as well as changed leaf morphology when submerged [51, 52]. Thus,
282 melaleucas are well adapted to permanently or seasonally wet habitats. In contrast, most eucalypts
283 are specially adapted to survive in arid environments with frequently occurring fires [53]. This
284 divergence in their habitat might have evoked distinct adaptive responses in eucalypts and
285 melaleucas.

286 The genome of another related species, *Leptospermum scoparium* (mānuka), has recently been
287 sequenced [54]. Phylogenetic studies on Myrtaceae indicate that *Leptospermum* and *Eucalyptus*
288 diverged 62 Ma [48, 55]. Thrimawithana *et al.* [54] reported high levels of overall synteny between *E.*
289 *grandis* and *L. scoparium*, with most orthologous regions being located on the same chromosome in
290 both species. Our analysis of the *M. alternifolia* genome also showed a high degree of shared synteny
291 with *E. grandis* and *C. citriodora*. This shared synteny at the scaffold level together with the great
292 number of orthologous genes among these three species suggest that this newly assembled *M.*
293 *alternifolia* genome is an excellent resource to increase our understanding of gene clustering and the
294 evolution of tandemly duplicated genes in Myrtaceae. Further comparative genomic studies among
295 the *M. alternifolia* genome, *L. scoparium* and all published eucalypt genomes [38, 42, 47, 56] could
296 elucidate the genomic mechanisms underlying the adaptive evolution of different Myrtaceae and
297 reveal lineage-specific gene family expansions. Families of interest include *TPS* genes and other genes
298 involved in stress responses. In *E. grandis*, for example, the majority of resistance (R) genes containing
299 nucleotide-binding sites and leucine-rich repeat domains (NBS-LRR) were shown to be organised in
300 tandem clusters [57], as well as genes encoding for S-domain receptor-like kinases (SDRLK) and MYB

301 transcription factors [38, 58]. These findings indicate that tandem duplication is an essential
302 mechanism for the adaptation to dynamic environments, especially for genes involved in responses
303 to abiotic and biotic stresses, and it should be compared how similarly these gene families evolved in
304 Myrtaceae and which selection pressures might have influenced their genome structure.

305

306 Conclusion

307 The *de novo* assembly of the *M. alternifolia* genome using the MaSuRCA assembler with PacBio long-
308 and Illumina short-reads resulted in a high-quality draft genome that was similar in length (362 Mb)
309 to the previously reported short-read assembly (357 Mb) [6] but with considerably longer scaffolds.
310 The N50 value was increased by a factor of 214. The completeness of the hybrid assembly was also
311 improved, as indicated by 6.1% fewer BUSCOs missing from the assembly, and a decrease of 5.6%
312 fewer fragmented BUSCOs relative to the previous draft. Alignments of *M. alternifolia* sequences to
313 *E. grandis* and *C. citriodora* indicated high sequence similarities and correlations in gene order among
314 the three Myrtaceae. The longer scaffolds of this new assembly will help to illuminate the genome
315 organisation in *M. alternifolia*, and allow further exploration of the significance of tandem gene
316 duplication as a mechanism of gene family evolution in tea tree and related Myrtaceae species.

317

318 Data availability statement

319 This Whole Genome Sequencing project has been deposited at NCBI GenBank under the accession
320 JAGKPW000000000. The assembly version described in this paper is version JAGKPW010000000.
321 PacBio raw sequencing reads are available under BioProject PRJNA702189. Supplementary
322 information regarding the computational methods has been summarised at protocols.io [12]

323

324 Abbreviations

325 bp: base pairs; BUSCO: Benchmarking Universal Single-Copy Orthologs; CDS: coding sequence; DB:
326 database; DNA: Deoxyribonucleic acid; HMW: high-molecular-weight; Kb: kilobase pairs; Ma: mega
327 annum; Mb: megabase pairs; N50: the collection of all contigs of that length or longer covers at least
328 half of the genome assembly; NCBI: National Center for Biotechnology Information; NG50: the
329 collection of all contigs of that length or longer covers at least half of the expected genome size; nt:
330 nucleotide; PacBio: Pacific Biosciences; RNA: Ribonucleic acid; SMRT: single-molecule real-time

331

332 Author's contributions

333 Formal analysis: J.V.; Funding acquisition: M.S.; Investigation: J.V.; Design of methodology: J.V., M.S.,
334 R.M.; Writing – original draft: J.V.; Writing – review & editing: J.V., M.S., R.M.; Supervision – M.S.,
335 R.M. All authors read and approved the final version of this manuscript.

336

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342 Competing interests

343 The authors declare that no competing interests exist.

344

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